

Decentralized Meta Frank Wolfe for Online Neural Network Optimization

Abstract—The design of decentralized learning algorithms is important in the fast-growing world in which data are distributed over participants with limited local computation resources and communication. In this direction, we propose an online algorithm minimizing non-convex loss functions aggregated from individual data/models distributed over a network. We provide the theoretical performance guarantee of our algorithm and demonstrate its utility on a real life smart building.

Index Terms—Decentralized Online Learning, Non Convex Functions, Neural Networks, Smart building application.

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the recent years, it has been witnessed a tremendous growth of data, in particular collected near the data-generating devices such as IoT sensors. The data is then transferred across a network (such as Internet) to be processed in some remote data-processing centers. At the end, the results of such computations, in particular learning procedures, are transferred back through the network to the original devices. This way of processing data has two major drawbacks. First, it has huge communication overheads, causing high energy consumption. Second, this model has a limited ability for handling real-time data where frequent to-and-from data movements can easily overwhelm the entire system.

Machine learning (ML in short) has been proposed recently to address these two challenges. A new ML paradigm, namely *federated learning* [1], has emerged naturally and has gained a lot attention. The main key factors behind the success of federated learning is its ability to perform computations close to the data locations, therefore avoiding huge communication overheads and lowering data privacy concerns. The federated learning framework

is particularly interesting in the context where huge amounts of data are needed to train the underlying machine learning models. Often, such data is generated locally across multiple nodes in online and distributed fashion. Thus, one of the main challenges while deploying AI solutions in federated learning framework is to design optimization algorithms that are robust under uncertainty and efficient in terms of both computation and communication costs.

In this paper, we consider federated learning in both *online* and *decentralized* settings. The study within this framework is a crucial step towards real-life applications and a challenging theoretical problem. More specifically, we study problems in the context of federated learning at the intersection of two rapidly evolving fields: namely *decentralized optimization* and *online learning*.

- Decentralized optimization focuses on the design and analysis of optimization algorithms that utilize local computation and communication among interconnected computing nodes. It plays a vital role in a wide variety of applications that arise in the domain of machine learning [2, 3, 4], control theory [5, 6], signal processing [7] and operations research [8].
- Online learning is a paradigm in machine learning for studying optimization problems to maintain robust solutions under the uncertainty of the future. This captures many real-world scenarios including in artificial intelligence and machine learning. In online learning, one needs to design an algorithm that repeatedly chooses a strategy from a given set so that the performance is as good as the best fixed action in hindsight. Online optimization has been widely studied in machine learning (see [9] as a starting point).

In federated learning, one particular constraint of local computations that one needs to pay attention is the computing capacity/resource at the local level. In general, it is desired to perform light-weight and low-complex local computations. Many decentralized algorithms have been proposed in online settings that are based on gradient methods (see more in related works). However, these algorithms require projections onto the constraint set that usually involves solving computationally intensive programs. Hence, in our work we aim to design competitive, robust algorithms in decentralized online settings and if possible, providing the flexibility to convert them to be projection-free.

Problem setting: Formally, we are given a convex set $\mathcal{K} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^d$ and a set of agents connected over a network and they are represented by a graph $G = (V, E)$. Let n denote the number of agents (vertices) in V that is $n = |V|$. A fixed neural network structure is shared among the agents. At time t , each agent $i \in V$ updates its own local neural network which yields a prediction $\mathbf{x}_i^t \in \mathcal{K}$. Subsequently, a batch of data is revealed exclusively to agent i and from its own batch, a non-convex cost function $f_i^t : \mathcal{K} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is induced locally. Although each agent i observes only function f_i^t , the cost of agent i is $F^t(\mathbf{x}_i^t)$ where $F^t(\cdot) := \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n f_j^t(\cdot)$, here F^t represents the cost function cumulated on all the batches. The objective is to minimize the total cost via local communication where each agent $i \in V$ can only communicate with its immediate neighbours, i.e., adjacent agents in G .

When the cost functions are convex, a typical measure is the *regret* notion. An online algorithm is $R(T)$ -*regret* if for every agent $1 \leq i \leq n$,

$$\frac{1}{T} \left(\sum_{t=1}^T F^t(\mathbf{x}_i^t) - \min_{\mathbf{o} \in \mathcal{K}} \sum_{t=1}^T F^t(\mathbf{o}) \right) \leq R(T)$$

As the cost functions in the paper are non-convex, we consider a stationary measure on the quality of solution based on the Frank-Wolfe gap [10, 11] and that can be considered as the counter-part of the regret in the non-convex setting. Specifically, we aim to bound the following terms, namely

convergence gap, for every agent $1 \leq i \leq n$:

$$\max_{\mathbf{o} \in \mathcal{K}} \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \langle \nabla F^t(\mathbf{x}_i^t), \mathbf{x}_i^t - \mathbf{o} \rangle \quad (1)$$

In the same spirit as the regret, the measure of convergence gap is defined compared to the stationary points in hindsight. Note that when functions F^t are convex, the convergence gap is always upper bounded by the regret. Moreover, when the problem becomes offline, i.e., all F^t are the same, the convergence gap measures the speed of convergence to a stationary solution.

II. OUR CONTRIBUTION

As a starting point, we consider the Meta Frank-Wolfe (MFW) algorithm [12] in the (centralized, convex) online setting and the Decentralized Frank-Wolfe (DFW) algorithm [13] in the decentralized (offline) setting. However, these algorithms work either in the online setting or in the decentralized one but not both together. The challenge in designing robust and efficient algorithms in both settings relies not only on the difficulty due to the uncertainty (online setting) and the partial information (decentralized setting) but also on the non-convex nature of the loss functions.

Building on MFW and DFW algorithms together with a subtle analysis, we present an algorithm that achieves the convergence gap of $O(T^{-1/2})$ (see Theorem 1 for the detail parameter dependency). The convergence gap of $O(T^{-1/2})$ asymptotically matches to the best regret guarantee even in the centralized offline settings with convex functions. Moreover, we show that our algorithm can be extended to capture the setting in which only stochastic gradients are available (instead of exact gradients).

Our work applies in the context of online neural network optimization amongst a group of autonomous learners. We demonstrate the practical utility of our algorithm in a smart building application where zones mimic learners optimizing a temperature forecasting problem. We provide a thorough analysis of our algorithms in different angles of the performance guarantee (quality of solutions), the effects of network topology and

decentralization, which are predictably explained by our theoretical results.

III. RELATED WORK

a) Decentralized Online Optimization: Yan et al. [14] introduced distributed online projected subgradient descent and showed vanishing regret for convex and strongly convex functions. In contrast, Hosseini et al. [15] extended distributed dual averaging technique to online setting using a general regularized projection for both unconstrained and constrained optimization. A distributed variant of online conditional gradient [9] was designed and analyzed in [16] that requires linear minimizers and uses exact gradients. However, computing exact gradients may be prohibitively expensive for moderately sized data and intractable when a closed form does not exist. In this work, we go a step ahead in designing a distributed algorithm that uses stochastic gradient estimates and provides a better regret bound than in [16].

b) Federated Learning: Our work is along the line of federated learning [1, 17] [18]. In the latter, offline centralized training (a start network where a central server is connected to several devices) is the currently dominant paradigm. However, decentralized training has been shown to be more efficient than centralized one when operating on networks with low bandwidth or high latency [19, 20]. In this paper, we consider a further step by studying arbitrary communication network without a central coordinator and the local data (so local cost functions) evolve over time.

c) Online machine learning in smart buildings: Ambience or power consumption data evolving through time in buildings in general is heterogeneous and represents complex spatio-temporal dynamics. Non parametric deep learning models for prediction [21], analysis [22], and control [23] save up on the time to hand-craft complicated or hard to model features. This primarily serves as the motivation for selecting non-parametric knowledge representation and train them in an online manner [24]. Usually the smart building hardware is distributed across a building and thus represent potential data sources of heterogeneous patterns.

Experimental evaluation on a smart building dataset show that federated learning [25] can help zonal models perform better in compared to isolated learning. In this work, we add a layer of autonomy and privacy by design amongst a group of collaborating learners thereby dropping the dependency of a central mediator for federation.

IV. CONDITIONAL GRADIENT BASED ALGORITHM

In this section, We first give an algorithm for the setting with exact gradients. Subsequently, we extend our algorithm to capture the more realistic setting with stochastic gradients.

A. An Algorithm with Exact Gradients

We first describe informally the main ideas of the algorithm. In the algorithm, at every time t , each agent i executes L steps of the Frank-Wolfe algorithm where every update vector (for iterations $1 \leq \ell \leq L$) is constructed by combining the outputs of linear optimization oracles $\mathcal{O}_{j,\ell}$ and the current vectors of its neighbors $j \in N(i)$. The solution \mathbf{x}_i^t for each agent/node $1 \leq i \leq n$ is chosen uniformly random among $\{\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t : 1 \leq \ell \leq L\}$. Subsequently, after aggregating the information related to functions f_j^t for $j \in N(i)$, the algorithm subtly computes a vector $\mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t$ and feedbacks $\langle \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t, \cdot \rangle$ as the reward function at time t to the oracle $\mathcal{O}_{i,\ell}$ for $1 \leq \ell \leq L$. The formal description is given in Algorithm 1.

Analysis. In the analysis, denote $\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t := \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \mathbf{x}_{j,\ell}^t$, we make use of the following lemma.

Lemma 1 ([13], Lemmas 1 and 2). *Assume that functions f_j^t 's are β -smooth, G -Lipschitz that is, $\|\nabla f_j^t\| \leq G$ for every $1 \leq t \leq T$ and every $1 \leq j \leq n$ and the diameter of \mathcal{K} is D . Then, there exists a constant ℓ_0 such that for every $1 \leq \ell \leq L + 1$,*

$$\Delta p_\ell := \max_{t=1}^T \max_{i=1}^n \|\mathbf{y}_{i,\ell}^t - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t\| \leq \frac{C_p}{\ell}$$

$$\Delta d_\ell := \max_{t=1}^T \max_{i=1}^n \|\mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \nabla f_j^t(\mathbf{y}_{j,\ell}^t)\| \leq \frac{C_d}{\ell}$$

where $C_p = \ell_0 \sqrt{n} D$ and $C_d = \sqrt{n} \cdot \max \left\{ 2 \left(\frac{\ell_0 \sqrt{n} D}{\ell} + D \right) \beta; |\lambda_2(W)| \ell_0 \left(\frac{\beta D}{1 - |\lambda_2(W)|} + G \right) \right\}$

Algorithm 1 Decentralized online algorithm

Input: A convex set \mathcal{K} , a time horizon T , a parameter L , online linear optimization oracles $\mathcal{O}_{i,1}, \dots, \mathcal{O}_{i,L}$ for each player $1 \leq i \leq n$, step sizes $\eta_\ell \in (0, 1)$ for all $1 \leq \ell \leq L$

- 1: Initialize linear optimizing oracle $\mathcal{O}_{i,\ell}$ for all $1 \leq \ell \leq L$
 - 2: **for** $t = 1$ to T **do**
 - 3: **for** every agent $1 \leq i \leq n$ **do**
 - 4: Initialize arbitrarily $\mathbf{x}_{i,1}^t \in \mathcal{K}$
 - 5: **for** $1 \leq \ell \leq L$ **do**
 - 6: Let $\mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t$ be the output of oracle $\mathcal{O}_{i,\ell}$ at time step t .
 - 7: Send $\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t$ to all neighbours $N(i)$
 - 8: Once receiving $\mathbf{x}_{j,\ell}^t$ from all neighbours $j \in N(i)$, set $\mathbf{y}_{i,\ell}^t \leftarrow \sum_j W_{ij} \mathbf{x}_{j,\ell}^t$.
 - 9: Compute $\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell+1}^t \leftarrow (1-\eta_\ell)\mathbf{y}_{i,\ell}^t + \eta_\ell \mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t$.
 - 10: **end for**
 - 11: Choose $\mathbf{x}_i^t \leftarrow \mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t$ for $1 \leq \ell \leq L$ with probability $\frac{1}{L}$ and play \mathbf{x}_i^t
 - 12: Receive function f_i^t
 - 13: Set $\mathbf{g}_{i,1}^t \leftarrow \nabla f_i^t(\mathbf{x}_{i,1}^t)$
 - 14: **for** $1 \leq \ell \leq L$ **do**
 - 15: Send $\mathbf{g}_{i,\ell}^t$ to all neighbours $N(i)$.
 - 16: After receiving $\mathbf{g}_{j,\ell}^t$ from all neighbours $j \in N(i)$, compute $\mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t \leftarrow \sum_{j \in N(i)} W_{ij} \mathbf{g}_{j,\ell}^t$ and $\mathbf{g}_{i,\ell+1}^t \leftarrow (\nabla f_i^t(\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell+1}^t) - \nabla f_i^t(\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t)) + \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t$.
 - 17: Feedback function $\langle \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t, \cdot \rangle$ to oracles $\mathcal{O}_{i,\ell}$. (The cost of the oracle $\mathcal{O}_{i,\ell}$ at time t is $\langle \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t, \mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t \rangle$.)
 - 18: **end for**
 - 19: **end for**
 - 20: **end for**
-

where $\lambda_2(W)$ is the second largest eigenvalue of W .

In order to bound the Frank-Wolfe gap for each individual node, we consider the *average* Frank-Wolfe gap, which is defined at every time $1 \leq t \leq T$ and for every iteration $1 \leq \ell \leq L$ as

$$G_\ell^t := \max_{\mathbf{o} \in \mathcal{K}} \langle \nabla F(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t), \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t - \mathbf{o} \rangle = \langle \nabla F(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t), \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t - \mathbf{o}_\ell^t \rangle \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{o}_\ell^t = \arg \min_{\mathbf{o} \in \mathcal{K}} \langle \nabla F(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t), \mathbf{o} \rangle$.

Lemma 2. For all $1 \leq i \leq n$, for every iteration $1 \leq \ell \leq L$, it holds that

$$\begin{aligned} & \max_{\mathbf{o} \in \mathcal{K}} \langle \nabla F_t(\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t), \mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t - \mathbf{o} \rangle \\ & \leq \max_{\mathbf{o} \in \mathcal{K}} \langle \nabla F_t(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t), \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t - \mathbf{o} \rangle + (\beta D + G) C_p \frac{\log L}{L}. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 1. Let \mathcal{K} be a convex set with diameter D . Assume that functions F^t (possibly non convex) are β -smooth and G -Lipschitz for every t . With the choice of step size $\eta_\ell = \min(1, \frac{A}{\ell^\alpha})$ where $A \geq 0$ and $\alpha \in (0, 1)$. Then, Algorithm 1 guarantees that for all $1 \leq i \leq n$:

$$\begin{aligned} & \max_{\mathbf{o} \in \mathcal{K}} \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{x}_i^t} [\langle \nabla F^t(\mathbf{x}_i^t), \mathbf{x}_i^t - \mathbf{o} \rangle] \\ & \leq \frac{GDA^{-1}}{L^{1-\alpha}} + \frac{AD^2\beta/2}{L^\alpha(1-\alpha)} + O(\mathcal{R}^T) \\ & \quad + ((\beta C_p + C_d)D + (\beta D + G)C_p) \frac{\log L}{L} \end{aligned}$$

where \mathcal{R}^T is the regret of online linear minimization oracles. Choosing $L = T$, $\alpha = 1/2$ and oracles as gradient descent or follow-the-perturbed-leader with regret $\mathcal{R}^T = O(T^{-1/2})$, we obtain the gap convergence rate of $O(T^{-1/2})$.

Proof. By β -smoothness, $\forall \ell \in \{1, \dots, L\}$:

$$\begin{aligned} & F^t(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_{\ell+1}^t) - F^t(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t) \\ & \leq \langle \nabla F^t(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t), \bar{\mathbf{x}}_{\ell+1}^t - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t \rangle + \frac{\beta}{2} \|\bar{\mathbf{x}}_{\ell+1}^t - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t\|^2 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Using Lemma 3, the inner product in (3) can be re-written as :

$$\begin{aligned} & \langle \nabla F^t(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t), \bar{\mathbf{x}}_{\ell+1}^t - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t \rangle \\ & = \eta_\ell \left\langle \nabla F^t(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t), \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t \right\rangle \\ & = \eta_\ell \left\langle \nabla F^t(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t), \frac{1}{n} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t - n \cdot \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t \right) \right\rangle \\ & = \frac{\eta_\ell}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \langle \nabla F^t(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t), \mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t \rangle \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Let \mathbf{o}_ℓ^t be such that $\mathbf{o}_\ell^t \in \arg \min_{\mathbf{o} \in \mathcal{K}} \langle \nabla F(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t), \mathbf{o} \rangle$. Hence,

$$\mathcal{G}_\ell^t = \max_{\mathbf{o} \in \mathcal{K}} \langle \nabla F(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t), \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t - \mathbf{o} \rangle = \langle \nabla F(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t), \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t - \mathbf{o}_\ell^t \rangle$$

We have :

$$\begin{aligned} & \langle \nabla F^t(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t), \mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t \rangle \\ &= \langle \nabla F^t(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t) - \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t, \mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t - \mathbf{o}_\ell^t \rangle \\ & \quad + \langle \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t, \mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t - \mathbf{o}_\ell^t \rangle \\ & \quad + \langle \nabla F^t(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t), \mathbf{o}_\ell^t - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t \rangle \\ & \leq \|\nabla F^t(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t) - \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t\| \|\mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t - \mathbf{o}_\ell^t\| \\ & \quad + \langle \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t, \mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t - \mathbf{o}_\ell^t \rangle \\ & \quad + \langle \nabla F^t(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t), \mathbf{o}_\ell^t - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t \rangle \\ & \leq \|\nabla F^t(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t) - \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t\| D + \langle \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t, \mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t - \mathbf{o}_\ell^t \rangle \\ & \quad + \langle \nabla F^t(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t), \mathbf{o}_\ell^t - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t \rangle. \end{aligned}$$

where we use Cauchy-Schwarz in the first inequality. Using Lemma 1 and β -smoothness of F^t ,

$$\begin{aligned} & \|\nabla F^t(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t) - \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t\| \\ & \leq \|\nabla F^t(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t) - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \nabla f_i^t(\mathbf{y}_{i,\ell}^t)\| \\ & \quad + \left\| \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \nabla f_i^t(\mathbf{y}_{i,\ell}^t) - \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t \right\| \\ & \leq \left\| \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \nabla f_i^t(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t) - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \nabla f_i^t(\mathbf{y}_{i,\ell}^t) \right\| \\ & \quad + \left\| \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \nabla f_i^t(\mathbf{y}_{i,\ell}^t) - \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t \right\| \\ & \leq \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \|\nabla f_i^t(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t) - \nabla f_i^t(\mathbf{y}_{i,\ell}^t)\| \\ & \quad + \left\| \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \nabla f_i^t(\mathbf{y}_{i,\ell}^t) - \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t \right\| \\ & \leq \frac{\beta}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \|\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t - \mathbf{y}_{i,\ell}^t\| \quad (\text{by } \beta \text{ smoothness}) \\ & \quad + \left\| \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \nabla f_i^t(\mathbf{y}_{i,\ell}^t) - \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t \right\| \\ & \leq \frac{\beta C_p + C_d}{\ell} \quad (\text{by Lemma 1}) \end{aligned}$$

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} & \langle \nabla F^t(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t), \mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t \rangle \\ & \leq \left(\frac{\beta C_p + C_d}{\ell} \right) D + \langle \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t, \mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t - \mathbf{o}_\ell^t \rangle - \mathcal{G}_\ell^t \end{aligned}$$

Upper bound the right hand side of (4) by the above inequality, we have :

$$\begin{aligned} & \langle \nabla F^t(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t), \bar{\mathbf{x}}_{\ell+1}^t - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t \rangle \\ & \leq \eta_\ell \frac{(\beta C_p + C_d) D}{\ell} + \frac{\eta_\ell}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \langle \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t, \mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t - \mathbf{o}_\ell^t \rangle - \eta_\ell \mathcal{G}_\ell^t \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Combining (3) with (5) and re-arrange the terms, as $\eta_\ell = \frac{A}{\ell^\alpha}$, we have :

$$\begin{aligned} \eta_\ell \mathcal{G}_\ell^t & \leq F^t(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t) - F^t(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_{\ell+1}^t) + \eta_\ell \frac{(\beta C_p + C_d) D}{\ell} \\ & \quad + \frac{\eta_\ell}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \langle \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t, \mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t - \mathbf{o}_\ell^t \rangle + \eta_\ell^2 D^2 \frac{\beta}{2} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Dividing by η_ℓ yields :

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{G}_\ell^t & \leq \frac{L^\alpha}{A} (F^t(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t) - F^t(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_{\ell+1}^t)) + \frac{(\beta C_p + C_d) D}{\ell} \\ & \quad + \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \langle \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t, \mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t - \mathbf{o}_\ell^t \rangle + \eta_\ell D^2 \frac{\beta}{2} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Let \mathcal{G}^t be a random variable such that $\mathcal{G}^t = \mathcal{G}_\ell^t$ with probability $\frac{1}{L}$. We are now bounding $\mathbb{E}_{\bar{\mathbf{x}}^t} [\mathcal{G}^t]$. By Inequality (7), using the definition of $\eta_\ell = \frac{A}{\ell^\alpha}$, G -Lipschitz property of F , we have (detail shown in Appendix)

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}_{\bar{\mathbf{x}}^t} [\mathcal{G}^t] & \leq \frac{GDA^{-1}}{L^{1-\alpha}} + (\beta C_p + C_d) D \frac{\log L}{L} \\ & \quad + \frac{1}{nL} \sum_{\ell=1}^L \sum_{i=1}^n \langle \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t, \mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t - \mathbf{o}_\ell^t \rangle \\ & \quad + \frac{AD^2\beta/2}{L^\alpha(1-\alpha)} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Summing the above inequality for $1 \leq t \leq T$ and note that $\frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \langle \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t, \mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t - \mathbf{o}_\ell^t \rangle$ is the regret of the oracle \mathcal{O}_i , we get

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \mathbb{E}_{\bar{\mathbf{x}}^t} [\mathcal{G}^t] &\leq \frac{GDA^{-1}}{L^{1-\alpha}} + O(\mathcal{R}^T) \\ &+ (\beta C_p + C_d) D \frac{\log L}{L} \\ &+ \frac{AD^2\beta/2}{L^\alpha(1-\alpha)} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

By uniformly random choice of \mathbf{x}_i^t (over all $\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t$ for $1 \leq \ell \leq L$) in the algorithm, we have (detail shown in Appendix)

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{x}_i^t} [\max_{\mathbf{o} \in \mathcal{K}} \langle \nabla F^t(\mathbf{x}_i^t), \mathbf{x}_i^t - \mathbf{o} \rangle] \\ \leq \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \mathbb{E}_{\bar{\mathbf{x}}^t} [\mathcal{G}^t] + (\beta D + G) C_p \frac{\log L}{L} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where we have used Lemma 2 and the fact that

$$\mathbb{E}_{\bar{\mathbf{x}}^t} [\mathcal{G}^t] = \mathbb{E}_{\bar{\mathbf{x}}^t} \left[\max_{\mathbf{o} \in \mathcal{K}} \langle \nabla F_t(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t), \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t - \mathbf{o} \rangle \right]$$

By Jensen's inequality, we have :

$$\begin{aligned} \max_{\mathbf{o} \in \mathcal{K}} \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{x}_i^t} [\langle \nabla F^t(\mathbf{x}_i^t), \mathbf{x}_i^t - \mathbf{o} \rangle] \\ \leq \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \mathbb{E}_{\bar{\mathbf{x}}^t} [\max_{\mathbf{o} \in \mathcal{K}} \langle \nabla F^t(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t), \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t - \mathbf{o} \rangle] \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

The theorem follows (11), (10) and (9) and setting $L = T$. \square

B. An Algorithm with Stochastic Gradients

In this section, we extend the previous algorithm to the setting where one has access only to stochastic estimates of gradients. The new algorithm is similar to algorithm 1 but now instead of using exact gradient, we use stochastic gradient estimates. (Note that the stochastic variables are denoted by the same letter as its exact counterpart with an additional tilde symbol). The only difference is the use of variance reduction (line 17) and so the oracle feedback (line 18) in algorithm 2.

Theorem 2. Let \mathcal{K} be a convex set with diameter D . Assume that for every $1 \leq t \leq T$,

- 1) functions f_i^t are β -smooth, i.e. ∇f_i^t is β -Lipschitz, (so F^t is β -smooth);
- 2) $\|\nabla f_i^t\| \leq G$ (so $\|\nabla F^t\| \leq G$);
- 3) the gradient estimates are unbiased with bounded variance σ^2 , i.e., $\mathbb{E}[\tilde{\nabla} f_i^t(\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t)] = \nabla f_i^t(\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t)$ and $\|\tilde{\nabla} f_i^t(\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t) - \nabla f_i^t(\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t)\| \leq \sigma$ for every $1 \leq i \leq n$ and $1 \leq \ell \leq L$;
- 4) the gradient estimates are β -Lipschitz.

Then, choosing the step-sizes $\eta_\ell = \min\{1, \frac{A}{\ell^{3/4}}\}$ where $A \in \mathbb{R}_+$. For all $1 \leq i \leq n$,

$$\begin{aligned} \max_{\mathbf{o} \in \mathcal{K}} \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{x}_i^t} [\langle \nabla F_t(\mathbf{x}_i^t), \mathbf{x}_i^t - \mathbf{o} \rangle] \right] \\ \leq \frac{DG + 2ADQ^{1/2}}{L^{1/4}} + \frac{2AD^2\beta}{L^{3/4}} \\ + [(\beta D + G) + (\beta C_p + C_d) D] \frac{\log L}{L} \\ + O(\mathcal{R}^T) \end{aligned}$$

Choosing $L = T$ and oracles as gradient descent or follow-the-perturbed-leader with regret $\mathcal{R}^T = O(T^{-1/2})$, we obtain a convergence rate of $O(T^{-1/4})$.

V. EXPERIMENTS

We demonstrate the utility of our algorithm on an online temperature prediction problem in a building.

A. Setting and Formulation

The data were taken from a building dataset contains ambient time-series captured on seven floors; each floor has four sensor-equipped zones. We set a zone-wise knowledge exchange via an undirected graph of n nodes/zones participating in the learning process. For every round t , each node i receives a batch \mathcal{B}_i^t of 32 time-series sequences corresponding to a look-back period 13 timestep to predict the temperature of the next timestep. At a resolution of 5 minutes, this corresponds to using 1 hour past data to predict the next 5 minutes. We extract the data from March 7th to April 20th for training, making the total iteration number equal to 360. We set L equal to the iteration number, $\alpha = 0.95$

Algorithm 2 Stochastic online decentralized algorithm

Input: A convex set \mathcal{K} , a time horizon T , a parameter L , online linear optimization oracles $\mathcal{O}_{i,1}, \dots, \mathcal{O}_{i,L}$ for each player $1 \leq i \leq n$, step sizes $\eta_\ell \in (0, 1)$ for all $1 \leq \ell \leq L$

- 1: Initialize linear optimizing oracle $\mathcal{O}_{i,\ell}$ for all $1 \leq \ell \leq L$
 - 2: **for** $t = 1$ to T **do**
 - 3: **for** every agent $1 \leq i \leq n$ **do**
 - 4: Initialize arbitrarily $\mathbf{x}_{i,1}^t \in \mathcal{K}$ and set $\tilde{\mathbf{a}}_{i,0}^t \leftarrow \mathbf{0}$
 - 5: **for** $1 \leq \ell \leq L$ **do**
 - 6: Let $\mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t$ be the output of oracle $\mathcal{O}_{i,\ell}$ at time step t .
 - 7: Send $\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t$ to all neighbours $N(i)$
 - 8: Once receiving $\mathbf{x}_{j,\ell}^t$ from all neighbours $j \in N(i)$, set $\mathbf{y}_{i,\ell}^t \leftarrow \sum_j W_{ij} \mathbf{x}_{j,\ell}^t$.
 - 9: Compute $\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell+1}^t \leftarrow (1 - \eta_\ell) \mathbf{y}_{i,\ell}^t + \eta_\ell \mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t$.
 - 10: **end for**
 - 11: Choose $\mathbf{x}_i^t \leftarrow \mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t$ for $1 \leq \ell \leq L$ with probability $\frac{1}{L}$ and play \mathbf{x}_i^t
 - 12: Receive function f_i^t and an unbiased gradient estimate $\tilde{\nabla} f_i^t$
 - 13: Set $\tilde{\mathbf{g}}_{i,1}^t \leftarrow \tilde{\nabla} f_i^t(\mathbf{x}_{i,1}^t)$
 - 14: **for** $1 \leq \ell \leq L$ **do**
 - 15: Send $\tilde{\mathbf{g}}_{i,\ell}^t$ to all neighbours $N(i)$.
 - 16: After receiving $\tilde{\mathbf{g}}_{j,\ell}^t$ from all neighbours $j \in N(i)$, compute $\tilde{\mathbf{d}}_{i,\ell}^t \leftarrow \sum_{j \in N(i)} W_{ij} \tilde{\mathbf{g}}_{j,\ell}^t$ and set $\tilde{\mathbf{g}}_{i,\ell+1}^t \leftarrow (\tilde{\nabla} f_i^t(\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell+1}^t) - \tilde{\nabla} f_i^t(\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t)) + \tilde{\mathbf{d}}_{i,\ell}^t$.
 - 17: $\tilde{\mathbf{a}}_{i,\ell}^t \leftarrow (1 - \rho_\ell) \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{a}}_{i,\ell-1}^t + \rho_\ell \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{d}}_{i,\ell}^t$.
 - 18: Feedback function $\langle \tilde{\mathbf{a}}_{i,\ell}^t, \cdot \rangle$ to oracles $\mathcal{O}_{i,\ell}$. (The cost of the oracle $\mathcal{O}_{i,\ell}$ at time t is $\langle \tilde{\mathbf{a}}_{i,\ell}^t, \mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t \rangle$.)
 - 19: **end for**
 - 20: **end for**
 - 21: **end for**
-

and $A = 1$, a smaller value of L is possible to reduce the training time. A min-max scaler is used to normalize the data and we apply a rolling window with stride 1 on the original time series.

We embed each node with a model built from

a two-layers long-short-time-memory (LSTM) network followed by a fully connected layer. Denote the output of the model i for a data sequence b at time t by $\hat{y}_{i,b}^t$ and its ground truth by $y_{i,b}^t$. Consider the ℓ_1 loss as the objective function :

$$\mathcal{L}(\hat{y}_{i,b}^t, y_{i,b}^t) = \begin{cases} \frac{(\hat{y}_{i,b}^t - y_{i,b}^t)^2}{2} & \text{if } |\hat{y}_{i,b}^t - y_{i,b}^t| \leq 1 \\ |\hat{y}_{i,b}^t - y_{i,b}^t| - \frac{1}{2} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Consider the constraint set $\mathcal{K} = \{\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^d, \|\mathbf{x}\|_1 \leq r\}$, where \mathbf{x} is the model's weight, d its dimension and $r = 1$. The (normalized) loss incurred by the data of agent i is :

$$\frac{1}{|\mathcal{B}_i^t|} \sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}_i^t} \mathcal{L}(\hat{y}_{i,b}^t, y_{i,b}^t).$$

The global loss function incurred by the overall data is

$$F^t(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{|\cup_{i=1}^n \mathcal{B}_i^t|} \sum_{b \in \cup_{i=1}^n \mathcal{B}_i^t} \mathcal{L}(\hat{y}_{i,b}^t, y_{i,b}^t),$$

that can be written as $F^t(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n f_i^t(\mathbf{x})$ where

$$f_i^t(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{B}_i^t|} \sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}_i^t} \mathcal{L}(\hat{y}_{i,b}^t, y_{i,b}^t).$$

Note that the non-convexity here is due to the non-convexity of $\hat{y}_{i,b}^t$ as a function of \mathbf{x}_i^t .

In the following section, if not specify otherwise, we call *loss* the temporal average of the global loss function F^t defined as $\frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T F^t$.

B. Prediction Performance

Figures 1 and 2 shows the loss and gap values for different network size. We make a selection of zones and floors to include in our network. We select zone 1, zone 2, zone 4, and 5 from the sixth floor for a 4 zone configuration. The 7 zone configuration combines zonal data on the sixth and seventh floor, where we drop zone 1 from the seventh floor. In the 10 zone configuration, we combine the data from the fourth, fifth, and sixth floor where we drop zone 1 and 4 from the fifth floor. Finally, the 13 zone configuration combines all four floors with the

same zonal selection. The implementation justifies our theoretical results about the convergence of the gap. Besides, we also observe the convergence of loss value, an expected implication of the gap convergence.

Moreover, by the analysis below, we also justify the particular thermal variation of the top floor compared to other ones. Table I reports the mean absolute error (MAE) and mean square error (MSE) between the prediction and the ground truth of the 4 presented configurations for three days. We set M the number of prediction points between the 21st and 24th of April and n the number of zones within one configuration. We call $\hat{y}_{i,m}$ and $y_{i,m}$, the predicted and the ground truth of model i for point m . The two metrics are computed as follows:

Mean absolute error :

$$\frac{1}{nM} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{m=1}^M |\hat{y}_{i,m} - y_{i,m}|$$

Mean squared error :

$$\frac{1}{nM} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{m=1}^M (\hat{y}_{i,m} - y_{i,m})^2$$

We observe that increasing nodes in a network does not always lead to better online performance. In fact, a 7 node configuration achieves the lowest MSE (0.65) and MAE (0.78) for floors 6 and 7. We see a 40 % drop in MSE and 20 % reduction in MAE for Floor 6 zonal models when 3 extra peers from floor 7 joined the group. We observe 19 % and 25 % increase in MSE and MAE values by adding zonal nodes from floor 7 to a 10 node group. This can be best argued by the fact that the top floor of a building has a non identical thermal variation with the rest of the storeys. A supporting observation is the zones of the top 2 floors of the building collectively generalize the best compared to any other configuration.

C. Effect of Network Topology on Learning

We study the effect of topology in learning for a 7 node configuration with a complete, cycle and line graph containing 28, 7 and 6 edges respectively and with 13 nodes having 78,13 and 12 edges respectively. For both 7 (Table II) and 13 (Table III) node

Fig. 1: Loss values of different network size on complete topology. (Plot on log-scale)

Fig. 2: Gap values of different network size on complete topology. (Plot on log-scale)

configurations, we observe that the complete graph yields the least amount of prediction error, mean absolute error $\in [0.66, 1.3]^\circ\text{C}$. However we note the peculiarity that the line graph can perform better than a cycle graph and has roughly a 10 % error margin compared to the complete configuration.

D. Effect of Decentralization

We are interested to understand the role of decentralization in terms of accuracy of zonal learners. Let $L_{MFW}(t)$ be the loss from Meta Frank Wolfe (MFW) at time t . The approximation ratio

$$A(t) = \frac{L_{DMFW}(t)}{L_{MFW}(t)}$$

Nodes	Floors	MSE	MAE
13	4567	0.85	1.26
10	456	0.71	1.01
7	67	0.65	0.78
4	6	1.5	0.99

TABLE I: Performance comparison between 4 network configurations

Topology	Metric	Mean	Variance	Max	Min
cycle	MAE	1.099	0.485	1.808	0.56
cycle	MSE	0.788	0.21	1.094	0.529
complete	MAE	0.778	0.381	1.478	0.27
complete	MSE	0.646	0.202	1.047	0.39
line	MAE	0.813	0.532	1.953	0.243
line	MSE	0.667	0.288	1.266	0.344

TABLE II: Impact of Networking on 7 learners configuration.

Topology	Metric	Mean	Variance	Max	Min
cycle	MAE	1.511	1.456	6.159	0.361
cycle	MSE	0.938	0.384	1.897	0.483
complete	MAE	1.257	0.82	3.64	0.32
complete	MSE	0.852	0.272	1.505	0.417
line	MAE	1.385	0.915	3.169	0.5
line	MSE	0.905	0.352	1.664	0.492

TABLE III: Impact of Topology on Temperature Forecasting Performance with 13 learners.

at time t is a heuristic to define how worse is our decentralized version compared to a centralized optimization. $A(t) \leq B_{max}$ will mean our algorithm performs no worse than B_{max} times of the MFW. Figure 3 shows that our algorithm performs slightly worse than MFW. On figure 4, we plot the ratio $A(t)$ for a 13 node network and show that $A(t) \leq 1.4$. The 7 node network has the closest approximation bounded by 1.35 which can be explained by earlier insights on performance accuracy. We notice that that the 10 node network performs worst till $t = 200$ and after $t \geq 250$ or 21 hours, the approximation ratio becomes close to centralised version with less than 20 % error.

VI. CONCLUSION

In the paper, we propose an online algorithm minimizing non-convex loss functions aggregated from local data distributed over a network. We show the convergence of the Frank-Wolfe gap, a standard stationary measure related to non-convex functions, in both exact and stochastic gradient settings. Besides, we utilize our algorithm to train a sequence to sequence deep learning model to forecast indoor temperature per zone. Experimental results from a real-life smart building data-set makes our offerings suitable for distributed setting.

Fig. 3: Loss values of decentralized and centralized Meta Frank-Wolfe (Plot on log-scale). We use data from 13 zones connected over a complete topology on decentralized setting (red curve) to compare with its centralized counterpart (black curve)

Fig. 4: Loss ratio of decentralized and centralized Meta Frank-Wolfe on different network size.

An interesting and related direction is to study the training of a bi-directional map between two features spaces U (temperature) and V (AC Energy Power). The challenge stems from modelling continuous but not necessarily differentiable data like electric power consumption that usually have fast response times with sharp edges and falls. Another interesting investigation will be the design of robust algorithm for the setting with dynamic communication graphs.

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APPENDIX

A. Technical details in Section IV-A

Recall that $\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t := \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \mathbf{x}_{j,\ell}^t$. First, we show some property of $\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t$'s.

Lemma 3. For every $1 \leq t \leq T$ and $1 \leq \ell \leq L$, it holds that

$$\bar{\mathbf{x}}_{\ell+1}^t - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t = \eta_\ell \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t \right) \quad (12)$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\mathbf{x}}_{\ell+1}^t &= \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{x}_{i,\ell+1}^t && \text{(Definition of } \bar{\mathbf{x}}_{\ell+1}^t \text{)} \\ &= \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n ((1 - \eta_\ell) \mathbf{y}_{i,\ell}^t + \eta_\ell \mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t) && \text{(Definition of } \mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t \text{)} \\ &= \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left[(1 - \eta_\ell) \left(\sum_{j=1}^n \mathbf{W}_{ij} \mathbf{x}_{j,\ell}^t \right) + \eta_\ell \mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t \right] && \text{(Definition of } \mathbf{y}_{i,\ell}^t \text{)} \\ &= (1 - \eta_\ell) \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\sum_{j=1}^n \mathbf{W}_{ij} \mathbf{x}_{j,\ell}^t \right] + \frac{1}{n} \eta_\ell \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t \\ &= (1 - \eta_\ell) \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \left[\mathbf{x}_{j,\ell}^t \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{W}_{ij} \right] + \frac{1}{n} \eta_\ell \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t \\ &= (1 - \eta_\ell) \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \mathbf{x}_{j,\ell}^t + \frac{1}{n} \eta_\ell \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t && (\sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{W}_{ij} = 1 \text{ for every } j) \\ &= (1 - \eta_\ell) \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t + \frac{1}{n} \eta_\ell \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t \\ &= \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t + \eta_\ell \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t \right) \end{aligned}$$

where we use a property of W which is $\sum_{i=1}^n W_{ij} = 1$ for every j . \square

Lemma 2. For every $1 \leq i \leq n$ and $1 \leq \ell \leq L$, it holds that

$$\max_{\mathbf{o} \in \mathcal{K}} \langle \nabla F^t(\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t), \mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t - \mathbf{o} \rangle \leq \max_{\mathbf{o} \in \mathcal{K}} \langle \nabla F^t(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t), \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t - \mathbf{o} \rangle + (\beta D + G) C_p \frac{\log L}{L}.$$

Proof. Fix $1 \leq i \leq n$ and $1 \leq \ell \leq L$. We have

$$\langle \nabla F^t(\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t), \mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t - \mathbf{o} \rangle = \langle \nabla F^t(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t), \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t - \mathbf{o} \rangle + \langle \nabla F^t(\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t) - \nabla F^t(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t), \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t - \mathbf{o} \rangle + \langle \nabla F^t(\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t), \mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t \rangle$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned}
\max_{\mathbf{o} \in \mathcal{K}} \langle \nabla F^t(\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t), \mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t - \mathbf{o} \rangle &\leq \max_{\mathbf{o} \in \mathcal{K}} \langle \nabla F^t(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t), \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t - \mathbf{o} \rangle + \max_{\mathbf{o} \in \mathcal{K}} \langle \nabla F(\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t) - \nabla F^t(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t), \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t - \mathbf{o} \rangle \\
&\quad + \langle \nabla F^t(\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t), \mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t \rangle \\
&\leq \max_{\mathbf{o} \in \mathcal{K}} \langle \nabla F^t(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t), \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t - \mathbf{o} \rangle + (\beta D + G) \mathbb{E} \|\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t\| \\
&\leq \max_{\mathbf{o} \in \mathcal{K}} \langle \nabla F^t(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t), \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t - \mathbf{o} \rangle + (\beta D + G) C_p \frac{\log L}{L}.
\end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 1. Let \mathcal{K} be a convex set with diameter D . Assume that functions F^t (possibly non convex) are β -smooth and G -Lipschitz for every t . With the choice of step size $\eta_\ell = \min(1, \frac{A}{\ell^\alpha})$ where $A \in \mathbb{R}_+$ and $\alpha \in (0, 1)$. Then, Algorithm 1 guarantees that for all $1 \leq i \leq n$:

$$\begin{aligned}
\max_{\mathbf{o} \in \mathcal{K}} \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{x}_i^t} [\langle \nabla F^t(\mathbf{x}_i^t), \mathbf{x}_i^t - \mathbf{o} \rangle] &\leq \frac{GDA^{-1}}{L^{1-\alpha}} + \frac{AD^2\beta/2}{L^\alpha(1-\alpha)} + O(\mathcal{R}^T) \\
&\quad + ((\beta C_p + C_d)D + (\beta D + G)C_p) \frac{\log L}{L}
\end{aligned}$$

where \mathcal{R}^T is the regret of online linear minimization oracles. Choosing $L = T$, $\alpha = 1/2$ and oracles as gradient descent or follow-the-perturbed-leader with regret $\mathcal{R}^T = O(T^{-1/2})$, we obtain the gap convergence rate of $O(T^{-1/2})$.

Proof. We complete the proof presented in the main text by giving the details of Inequality (10) and showing that from Inequality (7), i.e.,

$$\mathcal{G}_\ell^t \leq \frac{L^\alpha}{A} (F^t(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t) - F^t(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_{\ell+1}^t)) + \frac{(\beta C_p + C_d)D}{\ell} + \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \langle \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t, \mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t - \mathbf{o}_\ell^t \rangle + \eta_\ell D^2 \frac{\beta}{2} \quad (7)$$

one can deduce that

$$\mathbb{E}_{\bar{\mathbf{x}}^t} [\mathcal{G}^t] \leq \frac{GDA^{-1}}{L^{1-\alpha}} + (\beta C_p + C_d) D \frac{\log L}{L} + \frac{1}{nL} \sum_{\ell=1}^L \sum_{i=1}^n \langle \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t, \mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t - \mathbf{o}_\ell^t \rangle + \frac{AD^2\beta/2}{L^\alpha(1-\alpha)} \quad (8)$$

For all $\alpha \in (0, 1)$,

$$\sum_{\ell=1}^L \frac{1}{\ell^\alpha} \leq 1 + \int_1^L \frac{1}{s^\alpha} ds = 1 + \frac{L^{1-\alpha} - 1}{1-\alpha} \leq \frac{L^{1-\alpha}}{1-\alpha}$$

By definition of $\eta_\ell = \frac{A}{\ell^\alpha}$, G -Lipschitz property of F and Lemma 3, from Inequality (7), we deduce that:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{E}_{\bar{\mathbf{x}}^t} [\mathcal{G}^t] &= \frac{1}{L} \sum_{\ell=1}^L \mathcal{G}_\ell^t \leq \frac{L^\alpha GDA^{-1}}{L} + \frac{(\beta C_p + C_d) D}{L} \sum_{\ell=1}^L \frac{1}{\ell} + \frac{1}{nL} \sum_{\ell=1}^L \sum_{i=1}^n \langle \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t, \mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t - \mathbf{o}_\ell^t \rangle \\
&\quad + \frac{AD^2\beta/2}{L} \sum_{\ell=1}^L \frac{1}{\ell^\alpha} \\
&\leq \frac{GDA^{-1}}{L^{1-\alpha}} + (\beta C_p + C_d) D \frac{\log L}{L} + \frac{1}{nL} \sum_{\ell=1}^L \sum_{i=1}^n \langle \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t, \mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t - \mathbf{o}_\ell^t \rangle \\
&\quad + \frac{AD^2\beta/2}{L} \frac{L^{1-\alpha}}{1-\alpha} \quad (\sum_{\ell=1}^L \frac{1}{\ell} \leq \log L) \\
&\leq \frac{GDA^{-1}}{L^{1-\alpha}} + (\beta C_p + C_d) D \frac{\log L}{L} + \frac{1}{nL} \sum_{\ell=1}^L \sum_{i=1}^n \langle \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t, \mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t - \mathbf{o}_\ell^t \rangle \\
&\quad + \frac{AD^2\beta/2}{L^\alpha(1-\alpha)}
\end{aligned}$$

For Inequality (10), we use Lemma 2 with the following analysis

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{x}_i^t} \left[\max_{\mathbf{o} \in \mathcal{K}} \langle \nabla F^t(\mathbf{x}_i^t), \mathbf{x}_i^t - \mathbf{o} \rangle \right] &\leq \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{1}{L} \sum_{\ell=1}^L \left[\max_{\mathbf{o} \in \mathcal{K}} \langle \nabla F^t(\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t), \mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t - \mathbf{o} \rangle \right] \\
&\leq \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{1}{L} \sum_{\ell=1}^L \left[\max_{\mathbf{o} \in \mathcal{K}} \langle \nabla F^t(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t), \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t - \mathbf{o} \rangle + (\beta D + G) C_p \frac{\log L}{L} \right] \\
&\quad \text{(by Lemma 2)} \\
&= \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \mathbb{E}_{\bar{\mathbf{x}}^t} [\mathcal{G}^t] + (\beta D + G) C_p \frac{\log L}{L}
\end{aligned}$$

The last equality holds since

$$\mathbb{E}_{\bar{\mathbf{x}}^t} [\mathcal{G}^t] = \mathbb{E}_{\bar{\mathbf{x}}^t} \left[\max_{\mathbf{o} \in \mathcal{K}} \langle \nabla F_t(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t), \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t - \mathbf{o} \rangle \right]$$

That completes the proof of the theorem. \square

B. An Algorithm with Stochastic Gradient Estimates

Lemma 4 (Lemma 3, [26]). Let $\{\mathbf{d}_\ell\}_{\ell \geq 1}$ be a sequence of points in \mathbb{R}^n such that $\|\mathbf{d}_\ell - \mathbf{d}_{\ell-1}\| \leq \frac{B}{(\ell+3)^\alpha}$ for all $\ell \geq 1$ with fixed constant $B \geq 0$, $\alpha \in (0, 1]$. Let $\{\tilde{\mathbf{d}}_\ell\}$ be a sequence of random variables such that $\mathbb{E}[\tilde{\mathbf{d}}_\ell | \mathcal{H}_{\ell-1}] = \mathbf{d}_\ell$ and $\mathbb{E}[\|\tilde{\mathbf{d}}_\ell - \mathbf{d}_\ell\|^2 | \mathcal{H}_{\ell-1}] \leq \sigma^2$ for every $\ell \geq 1$, where $\mathcal{H}_{\ell-1}$ is the history up to $\ell - 1$. Let $\{\tilde{\mathbf{a}}_\ell\}_{\ell \geq 0}$ be a sequence of random variables defined recursively as

$$\tilde{\mathbf{a}}_\ell = (1 - \rho_\ell)\tilde{\mathbf{a}}_{\ell-1} + \rho_\ell \tilde{\mathbf{d}}_\ell$$

for $\ell \geq 1$ where $\rho_\ell = \frac{2}{(\ell+3)^{2\alpha/3}}$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{a}}_0$ is fixed. Then we have

$$\mathbb{E}\|\mathbf{d}_\ell - \tilde{\mathbf{a}}_\ell\|^2 \leq \frac{Q}{(\ell+4)^{2\alpha/3}}$$

where $Q = \max\{4^{2\alpha/3}\|\tilde{\mathbf{a}}_0 - \mathbf{d}_0\|^2, 4\sigma^2 + 2B^2\}$

Lemma 5. Given the assumptions of Theorem 2, for every $1 \leq t \leq T$, $1 \leq i \leq n$ and $1 \leq \ell \leq L$, it holds that

$$\mathbb{E}\|\tilde{\mathbf{d}}_{i,\ell}^t - \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t\|^2 \leq 12(\tilde{\beta}^2 + \beta^2)(2C_p + AD)^2 + \sigma^2$$

Proof. Fix an arbitrary time t . For any $1 \leq i \leq n$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbb{E}\left[\|\tilde{\mathbf{d}}_{i,\ell+1}^t - \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell+1}^t\|^2\right] \\ &= \mathbb{E}\left[\left\|\tilde{\nabla} f_i^t(\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell+1}^t) - \tilde{\nabla} f_i^t(\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t) - (\nabla f_i^t(\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell+1}^t) - \nabla f_i^t(\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t)) + (\tilde{\mathbf{d}}_{i,\ell}^t - \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t)\right\|^2\right] \\ &= \mathbb{E}\left[\left\|\tilde{\nabla} f_i^t(\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell+1}^t) - \tilde{\nabla} f_i^t(\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t) - (\nabla f_i^t(\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell+1}^t) - \nabla f_i^t(\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t))\right\|^2 + \|\tilde{\mathbf{d}}_{i,\ell}^t - \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t\|^2\right] \\ &\leq \mathbb{E}\left[4(\|\tilde{\nabla} f_i^t(\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell+1}^t) - \tilde{\nabla} f_i^t(\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t)\|^2 + \|\nabla f_i^t(\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell+1}^t) - \nabla f_i^t(\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t)\|^2) + \|\tilde{\mathbf{d}}_{i,\ell}^t - \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t\|^2\right] \\ &\leq \mathbb{E}\left[4(\tilde{\beta}^2 + \beta^2)\|\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell+1}^t - \mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t\|^2 + \|\tilde{\mathbf{d}}_{i,\ell}^t - \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t\|^2\right] \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

The second equality holds since $\mathbb{E}[\tilde{\nabla} f_i^t(\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell+1}^t) - \tilde{\nabla} f_i^t(\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t) - (\nabla f_i^t(\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell+1}^t) - \nabla f_i^t(\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t))] = 0$. The first inequality follows the fact that $\|\mathbf{a} + \mathbf{b}\|^2 \leq 4(\|\mathbf{a}\|^2 + \|\mathbf{b}\|^2)$. The last inequality is due to the β -Lipschitz and $\tilde{\nabla}$ -Lipschitz of ∇f_i^t and $\tilde{\nabla} f_i^t$, respectively.

Moreover,

$$\begin{aligned} \|\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell+1}^t - \mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t\| &\leq \|\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell+1}^t - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_{\ell+1}^t\| + \|\bar{\mathbf{x}}_{\ell+1}^t - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t\| + \|\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t - \mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t\| \\ &\leq \frac{2C_p}{\ell} + \|\bar{\mathbf{x}}_{\ell+1}^t - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t\| \end{aligned} \quad (\text{by Lemma 1})$$

$$= \frac{2C_p}{\ell} + \eta_\ell \left\| \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \mathbf{v}_{j,\ell}^t - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t \right\| \quad (\text{by Lemma 3})$$

$$\leq \frac{2C_p}{\ell} + \eta_\ell D \quad (14)$$

$$\leq \frac{2C_p + AD}{\ell^{3/4}} \quad (15)$$

where in the last inequality, $\|\frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \mathbf{v}_{j,\ell}^t - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t\| \leq D$ for every t, ℓ since both $\frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \mathbf{v}_{j,\ell}^t$ and $\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t$ are in \mathcal{K} . Therefore, combining (13) and (15), we get

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\|\tilde{\mathbf{d}}_{i,\ell+1}^t - \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell+1}^t\|^2 \right] \leq 4(\tilde{\beta}^2 + \beta^2) \frac{(2C_p + AD)^2}{\ell^{3/2}} + \|\tilde{\mathbf{d}}_{i,\ell}^t - \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t\|^2 \quad (16)$$

Applying (16) recursively on ℓ , we deduce that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E} \left[\|\tilde{\mathbf{d}}_{i,\ell+1}^t - \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell+1}^t\|^2 \right] &\leq 4(\tilde{\beta}^2 + \beta^2)(2C_p + AD)^2 \sum_{l=1}^{\ell} \frac{1}{l^{3/2}} + \|\tilde{\mathbf{d}}_{i,1}^t - \mathbf{d}_{i,1}^t\|^2 \\ &\leq 12(\tilde{\beta}^2 + \beta^2)(2C_p + AD)^2 + \|\tilde{\mathbf{d}}_{i,1}^t - \mathbf{d}_{i,1}^t\|^2 \end{aligned}$$

since $\sum_{l=1}^{\ell} \frac{1}{l^{3/2}} \leq 3$. Besides, for any $1 \leq i \leq n$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E} \left[\|\tilde{\mathbf{d}}_{i,1}^t - \mathbf{d}_{i,1}^t\|^2 \right] &= \mathbb{E} \left[\left\| \sum_j W_{ij} (\tilde{\mathbf{g}}_{j,1}^t - \mathbf{g}_{j,1}^t) \right\|^2 \right] \leq \sum_j W_{ij} \mathbb{E} \left[\|\tilde{\mathbf{g}}_{j,1}^t - \mathbf{g}_{j,1}^t\|^2 \right] \\ &= \sum_j W_{ij} \mathbb{E} \left[\|\tilde{\nabla} f_j^t(\mathbf{x}_{j,1}^t) - \nabla f_j^t(\mathbf{x}_{j,1}^t)\|^2 \right] \leq \sigma^2 \end{aligned}$$

since $\sum_j W_{ij} = 1$. Hence,

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\|\tilde{\mathbf{d}}_{i,\ell+1}^t - \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell+1}^t\|^2 \right] \leq 12(\tilde{\beta}^2 + \beta^2)(2C_p + AD)^2 + \sigma^2.$$

□

Claim 1. *It holds that,*

$$\|\mathbf{d}_{i,\ell+1}^t - \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t\| \leq \frac{B}{(\ell + 3)^\alpha}$$

where $B = 4C_d + 2\beta [2C_p + AD]$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} \|\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_{\ell-1}^t\| &= \eta_\ell \left\| \left[\frac{1}{n} \left(\sum_{j=1}^n \mathbf{v}_{j,\ell-1}^t \right) \right] - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_{\ell-1}^t \right\| && \text{(By Lemma 3)} \\ &\leq \eta_\ell D \quad \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \bar{\mathbf{v}}_{j,\ell-1}^t \in \mathcal{K}, \bar{\mathbf{x}}_{\ell-1}^t \in \mathcal{K} \text{ and } D = \sup_{x,y \in \mathcal{K}^2} \|x - y\| \right) \\ &= \frac{AD}{\ell} && \text{(Definition of } \eta_\ell = \frac{A}{\ell} \text{)} \\ \|\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_{\ell-1}^t\| &\leq \frac{AD}{\ell} && (17) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\|\mathbf{x}_{j,\ell}^t - \mathbf{x}_{j,\ell-1}^t\| &\leq \|\mathbf{x}_{j,\ell}^t - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t\| + \|\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_{\ell-1}^t\| + \|\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t - \mathbf{x}_{j,\ell-1}^t\| && \text{(Triangle inequality)} \\
&\leq \frac{C_p}{\ell} + \|\bar{\mathbf{x}}_\ell^t - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_{\ell-1}^t\| + \frac{C_p}{\ell-1} && \text{(By Lemma 3)} \\
&\leq \frac{C_p}{\ell} + \frac{C_p}{\ell-1} + \frac{AD}{\ell} && \text{(By equation 17)} \\
\|\mathbf{x}_{j,\ell}^t - \mathbf{x}_{j,\ell-1}^t\| &\leq \frac{C_p}{\ell} + \frac{C_p}{\ell-1} + \frac{AD}{\ell} && (18)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\|\mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t - \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell-1}^t\| &\leq \|\mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t - \nabla F_\ell^t\| + \|\nabla F_\ell^t - \nabla F_{\ell-1}^t\| + \|\nabla F_{\ell-1}^t - \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell-1}^t\| && \text{(Triangle inequality)} \\
&\leq \frac{C_d}{\ell} + \|\nabla F_\ell^t - \nabla F_{\ell-1}^t\| + \frac{C_d}{\ell-1} && \text{(By Lemma 1)} \\
&= \frac{C_d}{\ell} + \frac{C_d}{\ell-1} + \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \|\nabla f_j^t(\mathbf{x}_{j,\ell}^t) - \nabla f_j^t(\mathbf{x}_{j,\ell-1}^t)\| && \text{(Definition of } \nabla F_\ell^t) \\
&\leq \frac{C_d}{\ell} + \frac{C_d}{\ell-1} + \frac{\beta}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \|\mathbf{x}_{j,\ell}^t - \mathbf{x}_{j,\ell-1}^t\| && (f_j^t \text{ is } \beta\text{-smooth)} \\
&\leq \frac{C_d}{\ell} + \frac{C_d}{\ell-1} + \beta \left[\frac{C_p}{\ell} + \frac{C_p}{\ell-1} + \frac{AD}{\ell} \right] && \text{(By equation 18)} \\
&\leq \frac{2C_d}{\ell+3} + \frac{2C_d}{\ell+3} + \beta \left[\frac{2C_p}{\ell+3} + \frac{2C_p}{\ell+3} + \frac{2AD}{\ell+3} \right] && \text{(When } \ell \geq 7) \\
&= \frac{4C_d + 2\beta[2C_p + AD]}{\ell+3} && (19) \\
&\leq \frac{4C_d + 2\beta[2C_p + AD]}{(\ell+3)^\alpha} && (20)
\end{aligned}$$

□

Remark 1. By Lemma 4 and Jensen's inequality, we can deduce the following inequality

$$\mathbb{E}\|\mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t - \bar{\mathbf{a}}_{i,\ell}^t\| \leq \sqrt{\mathbb{E}\|\mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t - \bar{\mathbf{a}}_{i,\ell}^t\|^2} \leq \frac{Q^{1/2}}{(\ell+4)^{1/4}}$$

Theorem 2. Let \mathcal{K} be a convex set with diameter D . Assume that for every $1 \leq t \leq T$,

- 1) functions f_i^t are β -smooth, i.e. ∇f_i^t is β -Lipschitz, (so F^t is β -smooth);
- 2) $\|\nabla f_i^t\| \leq G$ (so $\|\nabla F^t\| \leq G$);
- 3) the gradient estimates are unbiased with bounded variance σ^2 , i.e., $\mathbb{E}[\tilde{\nabla} f_i^t(\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t)] = \nabla f_i^t(\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t)$ and $\|\tilde{\nabla} f_i^t(\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t) - \nabla f_i^t(\mathbf{x}_{i,\ell}^t)\| \leq \sigma$ for every $1 \leq i \leq n$ and $1 \leq \ell \leq L$;
- 4) the gradient estimates are β -Lipschitz.

Then, choosing the step-sizes $\eta_\ell = \min\{1, \frac{A}{\ell^{3/4}}\}$ where $A \in \mathbb{R}_+$. For all $1 \leq i \leq n$,

$$\begin{aligned}
\max_{\mathbf{o} \in \mathcal{K}} \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{x}_i^t} [\langle \nabla F_t(\mathbf{x}_i^t), \mathbf{x}_i^t - \mathbf{o} \rangle] \right] &\leq \frac{DG + 2ADQ^{1/2}}{L^{1/4}} + \frac{2AD^2\beta}{L^{3/4}} \\
&\quad + [(\beta D + G) + (\beta C_p + C_d) D] \frac{\log L}{L} + O(\mathcal{R}^T)
\end{aligned}$$

Choosing $L = T$ and oracles as gradient descent or follow-the-perturbed-leader with regret $\mathcal{R}^T = O(T^{-1/2})$, we obtain a convergence rate of $O(T^{-1/4})$.

Proof. By equation (8) in the proof of Theorem 1, we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{E}_{\bar{\mathbf{x}}^t} [\mathcal{G}^t] &\leq \frac{DG}{L^{1/4}A} + \frac{(\beta C_p + C_d)D \log L}{L} + \frac{2\beta AD^2}{L^{3/4}} + \frac{1}{nL} \sum_{\ell=1}^L \sum_{i=1}^n \langle \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t, \mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t - \mathbf{o}_\ell^t \rangle \\
&\leq \frac{DG}{L^{1/4}A} + \frac{(\beta C_p + C_d)D \log L}{L} + \frac{2\beta AD^2}{L^{3/4}} + \frac{1}{nL} \sum_{\ell=1}^L \sum_{i=1}^n \langle \mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t - \tilde{\mathbf{a}}_{i,\ell}^t, \mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t - \mathbf{o}_\ell^t \rangle \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{nL} \sum_{\ell=1}^L \sum_{i=1}^n \langle \tilde{\mathbf{a}}_{i,\ell}^t, \mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t - \mathbf{o}_\ell^t \rangle \\
&\leq \frac{DG}{L^{1/4}A} + \frac{(\beta C_p + C_d)D \log L}{L} + \frac{2\beta AD^2}{L^{3/4}} + \frac{1}{nL} \sum_{\ell=1}^L \sum_{i=1}^n \|\mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t - \tilde{\mathbf{a}}_{i,\ell}^t\| \|\mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t - \mathbf{o}_\ell^t\| \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{nL} \sum_{\ell=1}^L \sum_{i=1}^n \langle \tilde{\mathbf{a}}_{i,\ell}^t, \mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t - \mathbf{o}_\ell^t \rangle \tag{Cauchy-Schwarz} \\
&\leq \frac{DG}{L^{1/4}A} + \frac{(\beta C_p + C_d)D \log L}{L} + \frac{2\beta AD^2}{L^{3/4}} + \frac{D}{nL} \sum_{\ell=1}^L \sum_{i=1}^n \|\mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t - \tilde{\mathbf{a}}_{i,\ell}^t\| \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{nL} \sum_{\ell=1}^L \sum_{i=1}^n \langle \tilde{\mathbf{a}}_{i,\ell}^t, \mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t - \mathbf{o}_\ell^t \rangle \tag{(\mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t, \mathbf{o}_\ell^t \in \mathcal{K}^2 \Rightarrow \|\mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t - \mathbf{o}_\ell^t\| \leq D)}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{E} \left[\frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \mathbb{E}_{\bar{\mathbf{x}}^t} [\mathcal{G}^t] \right] &\leq \frac{DG}{L^{1/4}A} + \frac{(\beta C_p + C_d)D \log L}{L} + \frac{2\beta AD^2}{L^{3/4}} + \frac{D}{nLT} \sum_{\ell=1}^L \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{t=1}^T \mathbb{E} [\|\mathbf{d}_{i,\ell}^t - \tilde{\mathbf{a}}_{i,\ell}^t\|] \\
&\quad + \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{1}{nLT} \sum_{\ell=1}^L \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{t=1}^T \langle \tilde{\mathbf{a}}_{i,\ell}^t, \mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t - \mathbf{o}_\ell^t \rangle \right] \\
&\leq \frac{DG}{L^{1/4}A} + \frac{(\beta C_p + C_d)D \log L}{L} + \frac{2\beta AD^2}{L^{3/4}} + \frac{Q^{1/2}D}{L} \sum_{\ell=1}^L \frac{1}{(\ell+4)^{1/4}} \\
&\quad + \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{1}{nLT} \sum_{\ell=1}^L \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{t=1}^T \langle \tilde{\mathbf{a}}_{i,\ell}^t, \mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t - \mathbf{o}_\ell^t \rangle \right] \tag{By remark 1} \\
&\leq \frac{DG}{L^{1/4}A} + \frac{(\beta C_p + C_d)D \log L}{L} + \frac{2\beta AD^2}{L^{3/4}} + \frac{2Q^{1/2}D}{L^{1/4}} \\
&\quad + \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{1}{nLT} \sum_{\ell=1}^L \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{t=1}^T \langle \tilde{\mathbf{a}}_{i,\ell}^t, \mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t - \mathbf{o}_\ell^t \rangle \right] \tag{(\sum_{\ell=1}^L \frac{1}{(\ell+4)^{1/4}} \leq 2L^{3/4})} \\
&\leq \frac{DG}{L^{1/4}A} + \frac{(\beta C_p + C_d)D \log L}{L} + \frac{2\beta AD^2}{L^{3/4}} + \frac{2Q^{1/2}D}{L^{1/4}} + O(\mathcal{R}^T) \\
&\quad \tag{(\mathbf{v}_{i,\ell}^t \text{ are chosen by the online oracles with regret } \mathcal{R}^T)}
\end{aligned}$$

Recall that,

$$\mathbb{E}_{\bar{\mathbf{x}}^t} [\mathcal{G}^t] = \mathbb{E}_{\bar{\mathbf{x}}^t} \left[\max_{\mathbf{o} \in \mathcal{K}} \langle \nabla F_t(\bar{\mathbf{x}}^t), \bar{\mathbf{x}}^t - \mathbf{o} \rangle \right]$$

Therefore by lemma 2,

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{E} \left[\frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{x}_i^t} \left[\max_{\mathbf{o} \in \mathcal{K}} \langle \nabla F_t(\mathbf{x}_i^t), \mathbf{x}_i^t - \mathbf{o} \rangle \right] \right] &\leq \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \mathbb{E}_{\bar{\mathbf{x}}^t} \left[\max_{\mathbf{o} \in \mathcal{K}} \langle \nabla F_t(\bar{\mathbf{x}}^t), \bar{\mathbf{x}}^t - \mathbf{o} \rangle \right] \right] \\
&\quad + \frac{(\beta D + G) C_p \log L}{L} \\
&\leq \frac{DG + 2ADQ^{1/2}}{L^{1/4}} + \frac{2AD^2\beta}{L^{3/4}} \\
&\quad + [(\beta D + G) + (\beta C_p + C_d) D] \frac{\log L}{L} + O(\mathcal{R}^T)
\end{aligned}$$

Since max is a convex function, the theorem follows by applying Jensen's inequality on the left-hand side of the above equation. \square